

Retrofitting and Repairing principles of demolition

Bernhard Luthringshausen, Evelyn Temmel

BELT Architektur Buero
TU Wien, TU Graz

One-third of Austria's population lives in single-family and two-family houses [1], which is the most popular form of housing, particularly in rural areas. In fact, 64% of all buildings in Austria are single-family homes, and nearly half of these were built between 1945 and 1991 [2]. These buildings reflect the prevailing economic conditions, social values, and customs of their time, facilitated by affordable building land and low construction costs back then. This type of housing contributes significantly to high land consumption and increased energy demand. Both of which have risen dramatically in Austria, in part due to the extensive infrastructure networks and associated developments, such as retail parks, required to support this housing type. The result is the loss of agricultural land and natural habitats, leading to substantial environmental challenges [3].

In our practice, we explore how the existing building stock can be dealt with to reduce such high land consumption and the under-occupation of housing resulting from demographic change. A central tenet of this discussion is sustainable densification, with minimal increase in building volume. Here, demolition serves as an important tool to unlock the spatial potential of the building structure, reimagine internal workflows, and restore functionality, all with the aim of creating sustainable living spaces. In the two projects presented, we aim to adapt and repair the existing houses through simple, tactical measures based on four defined principles:

[1] Statistics Austria, ÖIR - Austrian Institute for Spatial Planning, and market research companies such as IMAS and GfK.

[2] Statistics Austria, "Zensus Gebäude- und Wohnungszählung 2021," 2021.

[3] BMK, "Handlungsempfehlungen gegen Bodenfraß," 2024. WWF, "Bodenreport 2024," 2024.

RETROFITTING AND REPAIRING

subtract

= demolish to repair

exchange

= demolish to replace obsolete parts

add

=demolish to introduce new spatial configurations

preserve artefacts

= sustain existing performing elements

Satellite view & street view of the former situation of House TAL.
Google Maps. Accessed July 2024.

Satellite view & street view of the former situation of House BAB.
Google Maps. Accessed July 2024.

The projects are located in suburban settings, and both were built in the 1980s. The house TAL is situated in a small town in Upper Austria, while the house BAB is located in a town near Vienna.

before: 1 person / 1 person | after: 4 persons / 2 persons

The previous owner of House TAL, moved into the house next door to take care of her aging mother and to make room for her daughter and family. The very large and introverted house needed to be modified on a low budget. The ground floor was opened up as much as possible to create connections and common spaces between the houses, activate neglected parts of the garden and create a sequence of public, semi-public and private spaces.

RETROFITTING AND REPAIRING

Upper Floor Plan

yellow = demolished
 red = new
 (N.B.: this is the colour coding required in Austria)

Ground Floor Plan

The submission plan shows the relocation of the main entrance to the northern part of the house and the kitchen to its western part. This intervention fundamentally alters the house's operational flow. 1 - by lowering the window sills to create full-height openings, the flow of the house was opened to the garden. 2 - the staircase and the balcony were still performing well and kept. 3 - a steel scaffold was added to serve as a transition between the indoor and the outdoor spaces.

CHAPTER 4 STRUCTURES AND CONSTRUCTIONS

subtract: By removing sections of the ceiling in the living room, the circulation, spatial connections and programmatic relationships were restructured to meet the needs of the new occupants.

RETROFITTING AND REPAIRING

preserve artefacts: elements that continue to serve their purpose are preserved, such as the old wooden staircase, the balcony on the south facade and the roof rafters and soffit. Initially retained by the clients due to financial constraints, these features were later appreciated as distinctive characteristics of the house. *add:* a new steel frame structure was implemented to serve as a transition-zone.

before: 2 persons | after (+13m²): 6 persons

House BAB needed to remain habitable on the ground floor during construction and previously overlooked building regulations had to be readdressed. It was important to create forms of cohabitation that respected the privacy and independence of the individual families while also creating space for joint living.

RETROFITTING AND REPAIRING

Constraints due to building regulations.

yellow = demolished
red = new
(N.B.: this is the colour coding required in Austria)

Ground Floor Plan

Three major interventions were carried out: 1 - a part of the roof was removed to lower the building's height in this section. 2 - the existing staircase was replaced with a new spiral staircase, allowing separate access to the units. 3 - a new room was added to the south.

CHAPTER 4 STRUCTURES AND CONSTRUCTIONS

[photo: tschinkersten fotografie]

subtract: to address the overlooked building regulations, the building height was reduced. By demolishing and lowering the western part of the roof the current regulations were fulfilled. This also created a view across the city to the landscape beyond. The change in the roof line allowed a better resolution of the house within its streetscape. [photo lower right: tschinkersten fotografie]

RETROFITTING AND REPAIRING

add: A new room was added to the garden side. With just 15m² added, the density increased from 2 to 6 people, accommodating now two families.
exchange: The spiral staircase optimizes space, providing a separate access to the units.
[photo lower left: tschinkersten fotografie]

Practices in Research #05 - Demolitions and Deconstructions - December 2024

Online Open Access Double-Blind Peer-Reviewed Journal for Practice-Based Research in Architecture

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Front and back cover images : © ARCH+, Summacumfemmer, büero Juliane Greb

Thanks to Orfée Grandhomme & Ismaël Bennani

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ISSN: 2736-3996

Practices in Research Journal
Rue des Palais 153 - 1030 Brussels
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